

1 **Quorum sensing inhibitory and antimicrobial activities of honeys and**
2 **the relationship with individual phenolics**

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1 **Abstract**

2 Recent studies have evidenced the role of cell to cell communication or quorum
3 sensing in the food spoilage, indicating that bacterial food spoilage could be regulated
4 by quorum sensing inhibitors (QSI). Owing to the importance of QS during bacterial
5 spoilage, much research is being focus on searching QSI, mainly natural products. The
6 beneficial properties of honey as antimicrobial and antioxidant agent have been widely
7 reported. However, as far as we known, the role of different unifloral honeys as a QSI
8 has not been jet reported. In this study, the inhibitory activity of 29 unifloral honeys was
9 evaluated using the bacterial model *Cromobacterium violaceum*. It was observed that all
10 the tested honeys were able to inhibit the production of acyl-homoserine lactones
11 (AHLs) produced by the *C. violaceum*. However, chestnut and linden honey samples
12 showed the highest anti-QS activity, while orange and rosemary were the less effective
13 inhibiting the production of AHLs. When honey samples from the same floral origin
14 obtained from different geographical regions were compared, they showed similar anti-
15 QS activity. Thus, it could be concluded that one of the factors which influences the
16 anti-QS activities, should be deriving from the floral origin and independent from the
17 geographic region. It was observed that unifloral honey samples showed “non-peroxide”
18 anti-QS activity, which was not linearly correlated with its total and individual phenolic
19 compounds. The obtained results showed that honey could have a potential use in the
20 food industry as food preservative due to its anti-QS activity, although further research
21 is needed to determine the active fraction of the honey responsible for the QS
22 quenching.

23

1 **1. Introduction**

2 Since ancient times, antimicrobial properties have been attributed to honey,
3 usually related to both the physical properties of osmosis and the antibacterial properties
4 of hydrogen peroxide and non-peroxide compounds (Taormina, Niemira, & Beuchat,
5 2001; Weston, 2000; Zumla & Lulat, 1989). Non-peroxide antibacterial activity of
6 honey has been associated to high sugar concentration, antioxidant and proteinaceous
7 compounds as well as other unidentified components (Lee, Churey & Worobo, 2008;
8 Mundo, Padilla-Zakour, & Worobo, 2004). Previous studies have linked the
9 antimicrobial activity of honey and propolis to flavonoids (including flavones,
10 flavonols, flavanones and dihydroflavonols) and other phenolics (mainly substituted
11 cinnamic acids and their esters) (Aljadi & Yusoff, 2003; Küçük, Kolayli, Karaoğlu,
12 Ulusoy, Baltai & Cadan, 2007; Povona et al., 2007). Due to these antimicrobial
13 properties honey has been generally considered as a natural food preservative (Mundo et
14 al., 2004).

15 Actually, up till now, investigations were restricted to whether or not honey could
16 kill or inhibit the growth of bacteria. However, as previously described for some plant
17 extracts, the antimicrobial properties of honey might only represent one facet of its anti-
18 infective potential (Adonizio, Downum, Bennett, & Mathee, 2006). The capacity of
19 honey to inhibit the interaction between the bacterium and the food may be also of
20 interest to avoid food spoilage. Gram, Ravn, Rasch, Bruhn, Christensen, & Givskov
21 (2002) defined the spoilage potential of a microorganism as the ability of a pure culture
22 to growth and produce the metabolites that are associated with the spoilage of a
23 particular product. It has been demonstrated that many bacteria are able to regulate the
24 expression of phenotypic characteristics as a function of cell density under the control
25 of chemical signal molecules. These auto-inducer molecules have been identified as

1 oligopeptides in Gram-positive bacteria and acylated homoserine lactones (AHLs) in
2 Gram-negative bacteria (Novick, Ross, Projan, Kornblum, Krieswirth, & Moghazeh,
3 1993; Miller & Bassler, 2001). The ability of bacteria to sense and response to
4 population density has been termed as cell-to-cell communication or “quorum sensing”
5 (QS). In fact, many bacterial physiological functions such as luminiscence, virulence,
6 motility, sporulation, biofilm formation, etc., are regulated by QS systems (Gram et al.,
7 2002; Lindum, Anthoni, Christophersen, Eberl, Molin, & Givskov, 1998; Winson et al.,
8 1995). For this reason, Rach et al. (2005) hypothesized that if QS systems regulate
9 bacterial mechanism in food spoilage then, inhibition of the communication underlying
10 the QS systems could be a good strategy to reduce or prevent the spoilage reactions.

11 Knowing the importance of QS during bacterial pathogenesis and spoilage,
12 research has been focused on inhibiting QS using bacterial biosensors and indicators
13 (Choo, Rukayadi, & Hwang, 2006). Among all the possibilities to interrupt the QS
14 system, the use of anti-quorum sensing (anti-QS) compounds can be of great interest to
15 avoid bacterial infections (Adonizio et al., 2006; Rice, Mcdougald, Kumar, &
16 Kjelleberg, 2005). Such “antipathogenic” compounds, in contrast to antibacterial
17 compounds, do not kill bacteria or stop their growth and are assumed not to lead to the
18 development of resistant strains (Otto, 2004). Except for the halogenated furanones
19 from the red alga *Delisea pulchra*, most of the identified anti-QS compounds of non
20 bacterial origin came from plant origin (Adonizio et al., 2006; Choo et al., 2006;
21 Teplitski, Robinson & Bauer, 2000; Bauer, & Teplitski, 2001). However, up till now,
22 only scarce information has been published regarding the QS-activity of honey
23 (Rasmussen et al., 2005).

24 Screening for AHL production from bacterial strains has typically relied on
25 bacteriological monitor systems, which consists of a phenotypic response, activate

1 through an AHL-receptor protein (Ravn, Christensen, Molin, Givskov, & Gram, 2001).
2 This is the case of *Chromobacterium violaceum*, a Gram-negative water and soil
3 bacterium highly sensitive to most short-chained unsubstituted AHLs (*N*-hexanoyl
4 homoserine lactone, HHL), which phenotypic response is the production of violacein, a
5 water-insoluble purple pigment with antibacterial activity (McClellan et al., 1997;
6 Steindler & Venturi, 2006).

7 The purpose of this study was to investigate the anti-QS and antimicrobial
8 properties of different unifloral honeys against *C. violaceum* to determine its possible
9 use as novel QS inhibitor (QSI). Additionally, the relationship between the individual
10 phenolic content of different unifloral honeys and its antimicrobial and anti-QS
11 activities has been also evaluated.

12

13 **2. Materials and methods**

14

15 *2.1. Honey samples*

16 Twenty nine honey samples of 14 different floral origins and 15 different
17 geographical locations were provided by the Agricultural Research Council (CRA-API,
18 Bologna, Italy) and Institute of Molecular Biology (Slovak Academy of Sciences,
19 Bratislava, Slovakia), which received samples from different raw honey beekeepers in
20 Italy and Slovakia, respectively. A Spanish commercial honey (Quexigal, Avila, Spain)
21 was also included in this study. **Table 1** lists the honey samples by floral source,
22 geographical location and country. During the experiments, samples were kept at 5 °C
23 in the dark in airtight containers. Prior to testing, a 66.6 % (w/v) working solution was
24 prepared diluting 2 g of each honey sample with 1 ml of sterile distilled water.

25

1 2.2. *Strains and culture conditions*

2 *Cromobacterium violaceum* wild-type strain CECT 494, obtained from the
3 Spanish Type Culture Collection (Valencia, Spain) was used to determine QS inhibitory
4 and antimicrobial activities. This wild type of strain produces and responds to the
5 cognate autoinducer molecules C6-AHL and C4-AHL, which makes this strain
6 excellent for screening (Adonizio et al., 2006; McClean, Pierson & Fuqua, 2004). This
7 bacteriological monitor system generates a phenotypic response by the production of a
8 purple pigment (violacein) when induced by the presence of AHLs. The bacterium was
9 routinely grown aerobically with shaking in Luria-Bertani broth (02-385, LB BROTH
10 acc. to MILLER, Scharlau Chemie, S.A. Barcelona, Spain) supplemented with 0.5 % of
11 NaCl and incubated at 30 °C for 24 h. Acylated homoserine lactone (AHL) plate assays
12 were performed using LB agar (02-385, LB BROTH acc. to MILLER + 07-004, Agar
13 Bacteriological, Scharlau Chemie, S.A.), using an agar concentration of 1.2 %.
14 Antibacterial activity of honey was carried out using LB agar (02-385, LB BROTH acc.
15 to MILLER + 07-004 Agar Bacteriological, Scharlau Chemie, S.A.) with a final
16 concentration of 1 % of agar.

17

18 2.3. *Inhibition of AHL Production by Honey*

19 The inhibitory activity of honey samples was assayed by the agar-well diffusion
20 test. Plates were made by adding approximately 10^5 cfu/ml of an overnight culture of *C.*
21 *violaceum* to the LB agar (1.2 %) (Scharlau Chemie, S.A.). Wells were filled with 20 μ l
22 of different concentrations (200, 400, 600 and 800 μ g/mL) of each honey. Plates were
23 incubated for 18 to 24 h at 30 °C prior to the determination of inhibition zone sizes by
24 contrast camera imaging (Synoptics, Cambridge, United Kingdom). The experiment
25 was carried out twice and there were three replications per treatment.

1 Flask-incubation assays were carried out to quantify the inhibitory activity of
2 honey samples. The bacterium was incubated for 18 h and inoculated to $OD_{600nm} = 0.1$
3 in Erlenmeyer flasks containing LB broth (Scharlau Chemie, S.A.) and LB
4 supplemented with different honey samples at different concentrations (200, 400, 600
5 and 800 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). The flasks were incubated at 30 °C in a shaking incubator. The
6 quantification of the violacein production was carried out following the protocol
7 described by [Choo et al. \(2006\)](#), where 1 ml culture from each flask was centrifuged at
8 13,000 rpm for 10 min to precipitate the insoluble violacein. Then, the culture
9 supernatant was discarded and the pellet was solubilized in 1 ml of DMSO, vortexed
10 until the violacein was homogenized, and centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 10 min to
11 remove the cells. Absorbance of each violacein-containing supernatant was measured at
12 585 nm in a UV–vis spectrophotometer (Hewlet Packard 8453). This experiment was
13 carried out four times and there were three replications per treatment.

14

15 2.4. *Antibacterial Activity of Honeys*

16 Antimicrobial activity of chestnut, linden, tilia, orange and rosemary honeys
17 against *C. violaceum* was evaluated. Ten millilitres of LB broth (Scharlau Chemie,
18 S.A.) was inoculated with 10 μl of a working culture of *C. violaceum* and the amount of
19 honey needed for each selected concentrations (200, 400, 600 and 800 $\mu\text{g/ml}$).
20 Inoculated honey solutions were mixed followed by incubation at 30 °C for 24 h.
21 Inoculated honey samples (1 mL) were diluted in 1 % sterile buffered peptone water
22 (BPW) (AES Laboratoire, Combourg, France) (1:10 dilution). Appropriate dilutions
23 were then spread onto LB agar (1 %) (Scharlau Chemie, S.A.). Colonies were counted
24 after 24 h incubation at 30 °C. Microbial counts were expressed as log cfu per milliliter.

25

2.5. *Measurement of Non-Peroxide Anti-QS and Antibacterial Activities of Honey*

Selected honey samples (chestnut, linden, tilia, orange and rosemary) were diluted at 66.6 %, with 0.1 M potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7) treated and untreated with catalase from bovine liver (13,500 units mg solid⁻¹, Sigma-Aldrich St Louis, MO) at ratio of 2,700 units mg solid⁻¹ per 1 g of honey. The anti-QS and antimicrobial activities of the selected honeys treated and untreated with catalase were carried out as above described.

2.6. *Phenolic Composition of Honeys*

For the extraction of phenolic compounds, honey samples (10 g) were dissolved with five parts of water (adjusted to pH 2 with HCl) until completely fluid. This solution was flushed through an activated Sep-Pak C₁₈ cartridge (Waters, Milford, MA), previously activated with methanol (10 mL) followed by water (10 mL). Then, the phenolic compounds were eluted with methanol (2 mL). The methanol extracts were filtered through a 0.45µm filter (Millex-HV13, Millipore Corp., USA) and stored at -20 °C until further analysis by HPLC-DAD.

Samples of 50 µl were analyzed by HPLC (Agilent 1100 Series, Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) equipped with a binary pump (G1312 A), a degasser (G1322 A), a photodiode array diode array detector (G1315 B) and a mass detector in series (Agilent Technologies). The samples were injected by a model (G1313 A) autosampler. The mass detector was an ion trap spectrometer (G2445A) equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) system. The nebulizer gas was nitrogen, the pressure and the flow rate of the dryer gas were set at 65 psi and 11 L min⁻¹, respectively. The full scan mass covered the range from m/z 100-1000. Collision-induced fragmentation experiments were performed in the ion trap using helium as

1 collision gas, with voltage ramping cycles from 0.3 up to 2 V. The heated capillary and
2 voltage were maintained at 350 °C and 4 kV, respectively. Mass spectrometry data were
3 acquired in the negative mode. Chromatographic separations were carried out a C₁₈
4 LiChroCART column (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) (RP-18, 250 x 4 mm; 5 µm
5 particle size) protected with a 4 x 4 mm C₁₈ LiChroCART guard column, with 1%
6 formic acid (A) and methanol (B) as solvents (99.9%, HPLC grade; Merck, Darmstadt,
7 Germany). Elution was performed with a gradient starting with 10 % B in A to reach 30
8 % B in A at 20 min, 45 % B in A at 30 min, 60% B in A at 40 min, 70% B in A at 45
9 min, 90% B in A at 60 min and then became isocratic for 5 min. The flow rate was of 1
10 mL min⁻¹ and chromatograms were recorded at 290, 320, 340 and 360 nm.

11 The phenolic compounds were identified according to their UV spectra, molecular
12 weights, retention time and their MS-MS fragments and wherever possible, with
13 commercially available standards. Hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives were quantified as
14 chlorogenic acid at 320 nm, flavonols, and flavones as quercetin and chrysin,
15 respectively, at 340 nm. Flavanones were quantified as hesperetin at 290 nm. All these
16 markers were purchased from Sigma (St. Louis MO), except chrysin from Carl Roth
17 OGH (Karlsruhe, Germany). The results were expressed as micrograms per 100 grams
18 of honey.

19

20 **3. Results and discussion**

21

22 *3.1. Inhibition of AHL production by honey*

23 Fifteen unifloral honeys, which are identified in **Table 1** with the symbol (*), were
24 tested for its capacity to inhibit the production of AHLs produced by *C. violaceum*. It
25 was observed that in most of the cases, honeys at 400 µg/mL exerted inhibitory activity

1 as estimated by the size of the inhibition zone (Table 2). However, at the lowest applied
2 concentration (200 µg/mL), only chestnut and linden honeys showed inhibition zones
3 due to the inhibition of AHLs production (Table 2). Figure 1 shows the observed
4 inhibition zones caused after the addition of different concentrations (200, 400, 600 and
5 800 µg/mL) of a selection of honeys (chestnut, linden, orange, rosemary and tilia) by
6 using the agar-well diffusion method. Taking into account that the agar-well diffusion
7 method is effective for the detection of AHL inhibition but it cannot reliably quantify
8 the relative amount of AHL present in a given culture, the flask-incubation assay was
9 carried out to quantify the inhibitory activity of honey samples (Blosser & Gray, 2000).
10 Thus, the anti-QS activity of different unifloral honeys was evaluated as their ability to
11 inhibit the violacein production by *C. violaceum* (Cho et al., 2006). As previously
12 observed in the agar-well diffusion method, honey samples showed concentration-
13 dependent inhibitory activity, and compared to control, all unifloral honeys showed a
14 significant drop in violacein production, even at the lowest tested concentration (200
15 µg/mL) (Fig. 2). On the other hand, chestnut and linden honeys showed the highest anti-
16 QS activity while orange and rosemary were the honeys which showed the lowest
17 inhibitory activity (Fig. 2). When the honey concentration was increased, the observed
18 differences among the anti-QS activity of the tested unifloral honeys were even more
19 marked. In fact, when 800 µg/mL of each honey sample were applied, *C. violaceum* was
20 only able to produce violacein in the presence of orange honey.

21 Additionally, differences in the anti-QS activity of honeys from the same floral
22 origin but obtained from different geographical origins were evaluated (Fig. 3). In this
23 experiment, and based on the previously obtained results, 5 unifloral honeys from up to
24 8 different geographical places, were selected (Table 1). Thus, chestnut and linden
25 honeys were selected as the best QSI and orange and rosemary honeys were selected

1 because they showed the lowest anti-QS activity. Tilia honey was included in the assay
2 due to its close relationship with the floral origin of linden honey. It was observed that
3 honeys from the same floral origin showed similar anti-QS activity regardless the
4 geographical origin (Fig. 3). The obtained results confirmed that the chestnut honey
5 showed the highest anti-QS activity despite the geographical origins.

6 It is well known that honey contains hydrogen peroxide, which present high
7 antimicrobial activity, so this compound could be also responsible for the anti-QS
8 activity observed in the unifloral honeys. To determine if the inhibitory activity of QS
9 was due to the presence of hydrogen peroxide, the experiment was repeated with the
10 addition of the enzyme catalase (Weston, Mitchell & Allen, 1999). It was observed that,
11 in general, the inhibitory activity was lower when the hydrogen peroxide present in the
12 honey was destroyed with the catalase, mainly at 400 µg/mL and higher honey
13 concentrations (Fig. 4). However, when compared to control, all the honeys remained
14 active even at the lowest concentration (200 µg/mL).

15

16 3.2. *Antibacterial Activity of Honeys*

17 The inhibition zones produced on lawns of the indicator strain and the inhibition
18 of violacein production could be the result of either (i) quenching of QS signals or (ii)
19 inhibition of cell growth, although growth inhibition would produce a clear halo versus
20 a turbid halo for the QS inhibition (Adonizio et al., 2006). To determine the main origin
21 of the anti-QS activity, the antimicrobial activity of chestnut, linden, orange, rosemary
22 and tilia honeys was tested at different concentrations 200, 400, 600 and 800 µg/mL. It
23 was observed that none of the tested honeys showed antimicrobial activity when applied
24 at 200 µg/mL (data not shown). However, the same honey concentration was enough to
25 significantly reduce the production of violacein when compared to control (Figs. 3 and

1 4). Table 3 shows the growth inhibition of *C. violaceum* after overnight incubation in
2 LB broth supplemented with 400, 600 and 800 µg/mL of honey. The observed
3 antimicrobial activity was concentration-dependent. In fact, the tested unifloral honeys
4 showed moderate inhibition against *C. violaceum* when applied at 400µg/mL, but it
5 significantly increased when the applied concentration was 800 µg/mL (Table 3). There
6 were also differences among the antibacterial activity of different unifloral honeys. In
7 general, when honey was applied at a concentration of 800 µg/mL, chestnut, orange,
8 rosemary and tilia showed similar antimicrobial activity reducing *C. violaceum* growth
9 by approximately 1 or 2 log units. However, linden reduced bacterial counts by 8.5 log
10 units, showing the highest growth inhibition. Thus, only high honey concentrations (600
11 and 800 µg/mL) were effective inhibiting growth of *C. violaceum*. When the same
12 experiment was repeated with the addition of catalase to eliminate the antimicrobial
13 activity of hydrogen peroxide, the antimicrobial activity of the honey samples was
14 reduced (Table 3).

15

16 3.3. Relationship between the Antipathogenic Activity and the Content of Individual 17 Phenolic Compounds of Honeys.

18 To determine the relationship between the antipathogenic activity and the
19 phenolic compounds of different unifloral honeys, the total phenolic content as well as
20 the content of individual phenolic compounds (hydroxycinnamic acids, flavonols and
21 flavonoids) were evaluated (Fig. 5). It was observed that all honey samples showed
22 similar but quantitatively different phenolic profiles (Fig. 5A). When the individual
23 phenolic compounds were evaluated, it was observed that the honeys which presented
24 the highest antipathogenic activity also showed a low phenolic content (Fig. 5B, C and
25 D). In fact, chestnut honey showed one of the lowest contents of hydroxycinnamic

1 acids, flavonols and flavanones (Fig. 5B, C and D). Tilia honey, which showed high
2 antipathogenic activity also showed one of the highest phenolic content (Fig. 5A). On
3 the other hand, some of the honeys with lower anti-QS activity, such as canola honey,
4 showed the highest phenolic content (Fig. 5A). Thus, in general, there was not a linear
5 relationship between the content of individual phenolic compounds and the
6 antipathogenic activity of the tested honey samples.

7

8 **4. Discussion**

9 The antimicrobial activity of honey as well as the variability in antimicrobial
10 activity of honeys from different floral sources have been widely reported
11 (Baltrušaityte, Venskutonis, & Čeksterytė, 2007; Lee et al., 2008a; Mundo et al., 2004;
12 Taormina et al., 2001). However, honey might have other antipathogenic activities, such
13 as the inhibition of QS. There is available data that provide evidence of the role of QS
14 in the food spoilage, suggesting that one way to prevent spoilage is the control of QS
15 (Ammor, michaelidis & Nychas, 2008). Several compounds have been identified as
16 QSI, although the most well-known examples of QSI compounds are the halogenated
17 furanones (Rasch et al., 2007). Unfortunately, these QS inhibitors are unsuitable for
18 human use as they are too reactive and may be too toxic to be used in medicine,
19 agriculture and industry (Bosgelmez-Tinaz, Ulusoy, Ugur & Ceylan, 2007). Hence,
20 there is a current need for the identification of new, nontoxic QSI compounds. Recent
21 studies have demonstrated the potential use of different plant extracts as QSI (garlic,
22 vanilla, pea seedlings, *Scorzonera sandrasica* and L-canavanine obtained from *Medigo*
23 *sativa*) (Bosgelmez-Tinaz et al., 2007; Choo et al., 2006; Teplitskiet al., 2000; Persson,
24 Hansen, Rasmussen, Skindersø, Givskov & Nielsen, 2005). However, as far as we
25 know, the ability of different unifloral honeys as QSI has not been reported.

1 In this study we observed that all the 29 honey samples inhibited the AHL
2 production when compared to control, even at the lowest tested concentration (200
3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). The anti-QS activity was concentration-dependent as the inhibition activity
4 increased with increasing honey concentration. Among all, chestnut and linden honeys
5 seemed to be the most efficient QSI. Therefore, significant differences were observed
6 among honey samples from different floral origin. On the other hand, when honeys
7 from the same floral origin but obtained from different geographical locations were
8 compared they showed similar anti-QS activity. Thus, it could be concluded that one of
9 the factors which influences both, the antimicrobial and anti-QS activities, should be
10 originating from the floral origin and independent from the geographic region.
11 Additionally, the antimicrobial activity of five different honey samples were evaluated
12 to determine if the inhibition in AHL production was due to quenching of QS signals or
13 inhibition of cell growth (Adonizio et al., 2006). It was observed that low
14 concentrations (200 and 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) of honey samples did not significantly inhibit
15 growth of *C. violaceum*. Thus, when low honey concentrations were applied, the
16 reduction in AHL production could be mainly attributed to quenching of QS signals.

17 The variability in antimicrobial activity of honeys from different floral origins has
18 been attributed to the botanical and geographical origins of honey and bee-origin
19 metabolism products, such as bacteriocin-like compounds and peptide antibiotics
20 (Baltrušaityte et al. 2007; Lee et al., 2008a, b; Mundo et al., 2004; Weston 2000). In like
21 manner and based in our results, the anti-QS properties observed in the tested honey
22 samples could be attributed to the same compounds. Furthermore, different honey
23 constituents have been characterized as responsible for the antimicrobial activity, such
24 as sugars, volatiles, beeswax, nectar, pollen and propolis (Weston, 2000; Mundo et al.,
25 2004). Previous studies reported that a significant part of the antimicrobial activity

1 observed in honey samples is due to their hydrogen peroxide content ([Lee et al., 2008](#);
2 [Taormina et al., 2001](#)). However, they found that catalase-treated honeys also showed
3 inhibitory activity, which may be attributable to non-peroxide related factors. In the
4 present study, catalase-treated honeys showed antimicrobial and anti-QS activities,
5 although this antipathogenic activity was lower when compared to untreated samples.
6 Therefore, it could be suggested that other factors of plant origin might be responsible
7 for the “non-peroxide” antipathogenic activity of honeys ([Weston, 2000](#)).

8 On the other hand, [Popova et al., \(2007\)](#) found a significant negative correlation
9 between the concentration of total phenolics in the propolis and the minimum inhibitory
10 concentration (MIC), which can be use as an evidence of the important role of phenolic
11 compounds in the antimicrobial properties of honey. What is more, high phenolic
12 content of honey samples has been also associated with high antimicrobial activity
13 ([Küçük et al., 2007](#)). Therefore, in the present study we evaluate the relationship
14 between the phenolic content of different unifloral honeys and its antimicrobial and
15 anti-QS activities. However, we did not found any relationship between the total and
16 individual phenolic contents of honey and their bioactivity. According with us, [Weston,](#)
17 [Brocklebank & Lu \(2000\)](#) determined that the phenolic components of the New Zealand
18 manuka honey were not responsible for the presence or absence of antibacterial activity.
19 Consequently, it could be concluded that the phenolic products from nectar, pollen or
20 propolis are only partly responsible for the residual non-peroxide antibacterial activity
21 of honey ([Weston et al., 1999](#)). However, other non-phenolic compounds associated
22 with their floral origin, such as different floral markers, could be responsible of the high
23 anti-QS activity of specific honey samples like chestnut and linden honeys. Therefore,
24 one might conclude that phenolic compounds contribute to the “non-peroxide” anti-QS

1 activity but the contribution of these components is relatively small as no linear
2 relationship was observed between the phenolic content and the inhibitory activity.

3 4 **5. Conclusions**

5 Few studies have been conducted to investigate the potential of different
6 compounds to reduce food spoilage by inhibiting bacteria cell-to-cell communication
7 and consequently the spoilage mechanisms. In the present work, the ability of different
8 unifloral honeys as QSI has been proven against the bacterium model *C. violaceum*. The
9 potential use of honey or specific honey components, responsible of the QS inhibitory
10 activity, as QSI is relevant to food industry as it might be used as a mild preservation
11 technique. Unifloral honey samples showed “non-peroxide” anti-QS activity and it was
12 not linearly correlated with the total and individual phenolic compounds. Thus, it is
13 clear that further research have to be carrying out to clarify which honey constituents
14 are responsible for the “non-peroxide” anti-QS activity.

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1 **Table 1.** Floral origin, country and geographical location of 29 honey samples.

Honey samples	Floral origin	Geographical location	Country
Acacia (*)	<i>Robinia pseudacacia</i>	Bologna	Italy
Canola (*)	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Bologna	Italy
Cherry blossom (*)	<i>Prunus avium</i>	Frossaco	Italy
Chesnut-1 (*)	<i>Castanea sativa</i>	Bologna	Italy
Chesnut-2	<i>Castanea sativa</i>	Bologna	Italy
Chesnut-3	<i>Castanea sativa</i>	Siena	Italy
Chesnut-4	<i>Castanea sativa</i>	Arezzo	Italy
Chesnut-5	<i>Castanea sativa</i>	Pistoia	Italy
Chesnut-6	<i>Castanea sativa</i>	Torino	Italy
Chesnut-7	<i>Castanea sativa</i>	Arezzo	Italy
Chesnut-8	<i>Castanea sativa</i>	Bologna	Italy
Eucalyptus (*)	<i>Eucalyptus spp</i>	Commercial	Spain
Lavander (*)	<i>Lavandula ssp</i>	Puimoisson	France
Linden-1 (*)	<i>Tilia argentea</i>	Sebecheleby	Slovakia
Linden-2	<i>Tilia argentea</i>	Bratislava	Slovakia
Linden-3	<i>Tilia argentea</i>	Banská Štiavnica	Slovakia
Lucerne (*)	<i>Mendicago sativa</i>	Bologna	Italy
Orange-1 (*)	<i>Citrus spp.</i>	Tornareccio-CH	Italy
Orange-2	<i>Citrus spp.</i>	Manfredonia-FG	Italy
Rape (*)	<i>Rapessed (Brassica campestris)</i>	Sebechleby	Slovakia
Rosemary-1 (*)	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Manfredonia-FG	Italy
Rosemary-2	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Tornareccio-CH	Italy
Sunflower (*)	<i>Helianthus annus</i>	Žembovice	Slovakia
Taraxacum (*)	<i>Taraxacum officinalis</i>	Bologna	Italy
Tilia-1 (*)	<i>Tilia ssp</i>	Bologna	Italy
Tilia-2	<i>Tilia ssp</i>	Minerbio-BO	Italy
Tilia-3	<i>Tilia ssp</i>	Torino	Italy
Tilia-4	<i>Tilia ssp</i>	Bologna	Italy
Tilia-5	<i>Tilia ssp</i>	Bologna	Italy

1 **Table 2.** Inhibition of AHL production of different concentrations (200, 400, 600 and
 2 800 µg/mL) of 15 unifloral honeys assayed by the agar-well diffusion test and expressed
 3 as the diameter (mm) of the inhibition zone obtained. The results are the mean of five
 4 replicates ± standard deviation.

UNIFLORAL HONEYS	HONEY'S CONCENTRATIONS			
	200 µg/mL	400 µg/mL	600 µg/mL	800 µg/mL
Acacia	0.0±0.0	82.7±11.0	89.3±13.3	134.0±2.0
Cherry Blossom	13.3±11.7	80.0±4.0	97.3±6.1	116.0±4.0
Chestnut	25.7±1.8	71.3±12.7	98.7±5.8	108.7±2.3
Canola	0.0±0.0	40.7±21.9	79.3±9.2	133.3±21.9
Eucalyptus	0.0±0.0	74.7±1.2	93.3±8.1	122.0±17.8
Lavander	6.0±10.4	63.3±4.2	93.3±6.4	124.7±3.1
Linden	15.1±8.2	54.0±17.4	85.3±6.1	124.7±2.3
Lucerne	0.0±0.0	67.3±1.2	97.3±1.2	112.7±5.0
Orange	0.0±0.0	80.7±5.0	103.3±4.2	128.0±3.5
Rape	25.3±1.2	75.3±2.3	105.3±2.3	107.3±2.3
Rhododendron	24.0±3.5	87.3±5.0	99.3±5.8	114.7±1.2
Rosemary	0.0±0.0	32.7±7.0	76.0±7.2	151.3±4.2
Sunflower	0.0±0.0	60.7±7.0	100.7±1.2	104.7±3.1
Taraxacum	0.0±0.0	78.7±7.6	102.0±4.0	112.0±10.4
Tilia	8.2±5.4	46.7±6.1	80.0±2.0	144.7±2.3

5

1 **Table 3.** Growth inhibition of *C. violaceum* after overnight growth in LB broth
 2 supplemented with different unifloral honeys at 400, 600 and 800 µg/mL and with and
 3 without the addition of catalase. Values represent cfu log₁₀ (N₀/N) ± standard deviation.

Honeys	Honey's concentrations	Without catalase	With catalase
Chestnut	400 µg/mL	0.23±0.18	0.29±0.10
Linden		0.53±0.49	0.32±0.06
Orange		0.07±0.0	0.20±0.17
Rosemary		0.11±0.06	0.06±0.07
Tilia		0.06±0.00	0.18±0.08

Chestnut	600 µg/mL	0.95±0.01	0.38±0.10
Linden		3.21±0.49	0.36±0.08
Orange		0.27±0.15	0.22±0.04
Rosemary		1.03±0.63	0.01±0.09
Tilia		1.29±0.56	0.11±0.08

Chestnut	800 µg/mL	1.51±0.09	0.93±0.12
Linden		8.54±0.08	8.54±0.08
Orange		1.09±0.14	0.86±0.11
Rosemary		1.83±0.04	0.94±0.06
Tilia		0.99±0.03	0.89±0.07

1 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

2 **Figure 1.** Anti-QS activity using *Cromobacterium violaceum*. Anti-QS activity was
3 tested using 20 μ L of different concentrations (200, 400, 600 and 800 μ g/ml) of
4 unifloral honeys of chestnut, tilia, orange, rosemary and linden.

5 **Figure 2.** Inhibition of violacein production by unifloral honeys (acacia, cherry
6 blossom, chestnut, canola, eucalyptus, lavender, linden, lucerne, orange, rape,
7 rhododendron, rosemary, sunflower, taraxacum and tilia) at different concentration
8 (200, 400, 600 and 800 μ g/mL). Vertical bars represent means of three replications \pm
9 standard deviation.

10 **Figure 3.** Inhibition of violacein production by unifloral honeys (chestnut, linden,
11 orange, rosemary and tilia) originating from different geographical regions at different
12 concentration (200 and 400 μ g/mL). Vertical bars represent means of three replications
13 \pm standard deviation.

14 **Figure 4.** Inhibition of violacein production by unifloral honeys (chestnut, linden,
15 orange, rosemary and tilia) at different concentration (200, 400, 600 and 800 μ g/mL)
16 with and without the addition of catalase to destroyed the honey content of hydrogen
17 peroxide. Vertical bars represent means of three replications \pm standard deviation.

18 **Figure 5.** Total phenolic, hydroxycinnamic acid, flavonol and flavanone content of
19 unifloral honeys (chestnut, linden, orange, rosemary and tilia). Vertical bars represent
20 means of three replications \pm standard deviation.

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1 **Figure 1.**

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1 **Figure 2.**

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1 **Figure 3.**

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1 **Figure 4.**

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1 **Figure 5.**

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